

SiCp/Al COMPOSITES FABRICATED BY SPRAY CO-DEPOSITION

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ABSTRACT

A new fabrication technique for particulate-reinforced metal matrix composites, spray co-deposition, was developed in this paper. SiCp/Al composites with the weight, say, 150kg or more, could be obtained. The good bond between particulate and matrix, high density matrix, low-segregation of SiC particulates and volume fraction of SiC particulates up to 15% were observed through the entire thickness of SiC/Al composites if the operation was performed correctly. Furthermore, the incorporation mechanism between SiC particulates and matrix and the atomized spray field were discussed.

Key words: metal matrix composites, particulate, spray co-deposition

1. INTRODUCTION

Particulate-reinforced metal matrix composites can be produced by many techniques, each of which has certain advantages coupled with disadvantages^[1].

An early fabrication technique is powder metallurgy method, which is reliable compared with other methods. However, it is relatively expensive due to its time-consuming process. Two further disadvantages are the difficulties of segregation of particulates and the fact that some desirable combinations are not possible. These disadvantages have limited the wide use of this method.

A different and more direct approach is to incorporate particulates in a melt of matrix, then cast the resulting composites. There are, however, considerable problems involved in dispersing particulates which are not wetted by the liquid matrix. In addition, segregation problems arise during solidification if there is a large difference in density between the constituents. This may also lead to the formation of brittle compounds at the interface between particulates and the molten matrix owing to the long contact time before freezing.

The new spray co-deposition process to fabricate particulate reinforced metal matrix composites offers a potentially attractive route as a result of a number of factors^[2~4]. First, because of highly efficient heat convection during gas atomization, relative low processing temperature can be obtained, and therefore deleterious interfacial reactions can be minimized. Second, spray co-deposited materials has some advantages associated with rapid solidification, namely: fine grained microstructure, increased solid solubilities, non-equilibrium phases and absence of macro-segregation. Third, spray co-deposition process has the potential of being utilized to produce large particulate-reinforced metal matrix composite ingots with low-segregation and high volume fraction of SiC particulates.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

The apparatus used for preparing particulate-reinforced metal matrix composites is schematically illustrated in Figure 1.

During spray co-deposition, a molten alloy stream is disintegrated into a fine dispersion of droplets using high velocity inert gas jet. Simultaneously, the SiC particulates are injected into the atomized spray by an appropriate injection procedure. The atomized droplets and particulates are then co-deposited onto a suitably designed collector. The collector is driven downwards at a speed of 35mm/min and rotates around the axis 50mm away from the axis of the atomized spray at a speed of 180r/min. The primary experimental variables used during each experiment are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Experimental variables used in the study.

Atomization pressure (MPa)	Atomizing gas	Pouring temperature (°C)	Flight distance (mm)	Metal delivery tube diameter (mm)	Metal flow rate (kg/min)
0.6~0.8	Ar	820	400	2.0	0.8

3. RESULTS

Three methods can be used to inject the strengthening phase into the atomized spray. Figure 2 shows diagrammatically the configuration that was adopted in the early experimental work^[3]. Tangential injection of the added particulates was performed between the liquid stream and the atomizing gas in order to reduce the loss of particulates. Other methods are to inject directly into the atomized spray from outside or alternative, through a central nozzle inside a liquid metal nozzle in the form of an annulus as shown in Figure 3. The first is the easiest method while the third is difficult to carry out but in practice at low metal flow rate. Thus, the first and the second were used in our study.

When the first method was used, w60 SiCp/Al composite ingots (150kg or more) could be fabricated and w60 SiC particulates (W60 means the mean diameter of SiC particulates is 60 μm) were distributed homogeneously in the matrix, as shown in Figure 4. The volume fraction of SiC particulates could be controlled in the range of 5~15%. However, when the mean diameter of SiC particulates is 10 μm , SiC particulate are too fine to be injected into the matrix by the first method. Therefore, the volume fraction of W10 SiC particulates in composite ingots is very low as shown in Figure 5.

In order to increase the volume fraction of W10 SiC particulates, the second method was used. SiC particulates were injected into the atomized spray through an annular nozzle at pre-selected spatial location as shown in Figure 6, where injection angle is 30° and injection distance is 0.21 meter. Accordingly, a typical ingot microstructure from a 6061 alloy containing 15% W10 SiC particulates is shown in Figure 7. It can be seen that the second method is the best one for incorporation of SiC particulates.

4. DISCUSSION

4.1. Atomized spray field

According to fundamental principles of gas dynamics, the atomized spray field is shown in Figure 8, which consists of three main parts: the main spray, overspray and the corner vortex flow. The main spray can be approximately considered gas-particulate two phase free afflux. Thus, the radius distributions of SiC particulates velocity and consistency in the main spray are shown in Figure 9 and Fig-

ure 10 respectively. It can be seen that SiC particulates' velocity and consistency become smaller and smaller as distance apart from the axis of the mainspray increases. Furthermore, the coarse SiC particulate tends to distribute near the axis of the main spray, while the fine SiC particulate tends to distribute in the outer area of the main spray or the overspray part because of the action of gravity. Overspray can be considered the extending part of the main spray, which contains finer SiC particulates than the main spray. The corner vortex flowrates forms due to fluid entrainment on the outer boundaries of the annular jets.

4. 2. Incorporation mechanism

There are two possible incorporation mechanism of SiC particulates into the matrix. One is called injection mechanism, the other is termed absorption mechanism.

In the injection mechanism, a SiC particulate is incorporated into the liquid layer of deposition surface as a result of adequate energy it have gained during flight. The depth that the SiC particulate enters into the liquid layer should be greater than the diameter of the SiC particulate. Figure 11 shows the forces acting on the SiC particulate by the liquid layer. Then, a simple force balance can be established on the SiC particulate.

$$m_p \frac{d\omega'}{d\tau} = -F_o - F_A - F_s \quad (1)$$

where F_o , F_A and F_s are the surface tension, the repulsive force and the resistant force, respectively, which are exerted on the SiC particulate by the liquid layer; m_p and ω' are quality and velocity of the SiC particulate respectively; τ is time. Subsequently, when the SiC particulate is incorporated into the matrix by injection mechanism, the lowest velocity at which the SiC particulate impinges on the liquid layer can be obtained by solving Equation (1),

$$\omega_2 = 2 \sqrt{\frac{2\rho_p + 0.5\rho_M}{\rho_p}} \sqrt{\frac{\sigma}{r_p\rho_M}} \sqrt{e^{1.5\frac{\rho_M}{\rho_p}} - 1} \quad (2)$$

where ρ_p and ρ_M are density of the SiC particulate and the matrix alloy respectively, r_p is the radius of the SiC particulate, σ is surface energy of the liquid layer, and ω_2 is the lowest velocity at which the SiC particulate impinges on the liquid layer. More detailed descriptions of the solving process of Equation (1) have been provided elsewhere^[5].

In absorption mechanism, a SiC particulate is absorbed by the atomized droplet and deposits together with the droplet. However, the possibility of absorption is very low because the SiC particulate is not wetted by the aluminum alloy. Therefore, if the SiC particulate is not treated by surface coating, it is impossible for the SiC particulate to be incorporated into the matrix by absorption mechanism.

4. 3. Discussion

The lowest velocity ω_2 at which SiC particulate is incorporated into the matrix by injection mechanism can be calculated from equation (2). The results are listed in Table 2. It indicates that the ω_2 value of the 60 μm SiC particulate is 23.52m/s while the ω_2 value of the 10 μm particulate is 57.60m/s.

Table 2. The ω_2 value of SiC particulates.

$r_d(\mu\text{m})$	5	10	20	30	40	50	60	70	80	90	100
$\omega_2(\text{m/s})$	81.46	57.60	40.73	33.26	28.80	25.76	23.52	21.77	20.36	19.20	18.22

As shown in Figure 2, when the second injection method is adopted, the velocity of the 60 μm SiC particulate arrives at 48m/s when it deposits; and the velocity of the 10 μm SiC particulate reaches 29m/s when it deposits. It can be seen that most of W60 SiC particulates can be incorporated into the matrix by injection mechanism, while only a few of the W10 SiC particulates, which are greater than 30 μm , can be incorporated into the matrix by injection mechanism. Furthermore, most of W60 SiC particulates from the annular nozzle will enter and disperse into the main spray because the size of W60 SiC particulates is in the same order as that of the gas atomized droplets. Therefore, W60 SiCp/Al composites with non-segregation and high volume fraction of SiC particulates can be obtained (see Figure 4). As for W10 SiC particulates, on the one hand, some of fine SiC particulates will enter into the corner vortex flow and overspray so that the amount of SiC particulates which enters into the main spray decreases greatly; on the other hand, of the SiC particulates which has entered into the main spray, some of the fine SiC particulates will distribute in the outer area of the mainspray or overspray during flight because W10 SiC particulates are smaller than the atomized droplets. Accordingly, W10 SiCp/Al composites which is made by the same process as W60 SiCp/Al composites have low volume fraction of SiC particulates as shown in Figure 5.

When the SiC particulate is injected directly from outside through an annular nozzle, the velocity of the 10 μm SiC particulate can reach more than 70m/s, which is greater than the lowest velocity at which the 10 μm SiC particulate is incorporated into the matrix by injection mechanism. Therefore, most of W10 SiC particulates can be incorporated into the matrix by injection mechanism, and W10 SiCp/Al composites with high volume fraction of SiC particulates can be obtained (see Figure 7).

5. CONCLUSIONS

The primary conclusions that may be drawn from this work are as follows.

- (1) SiCp/Al composites with the weight, say, 150kg or more, can be obtained by spray co-deposition.
- (2) W60 SiCp/Al composites with the volume fraction of SiC particulates in the range of 5~15% can be obtained when the first injection method (see Figure 2) is adopted, while W10 SiCp/Al composites, which is fabricated by the same process as W60 SiCp/Al composites, have low volume fraction of SiC particulates.
- (3) A new injection method (see Figure 6) is developed to inject SiC particulates into the atomized spray through an annular nozzle at pre-selected spacial location, and W10 SiCp/Al composites with the volume fraction of SiC particulates up to 15% can be obtained.
- (4) Theoretical analysis and experimental results indicate that most of SiC particulates are incorporated into the matrix by injection mechanism.

References

1. Ibrahim, I. A. , Mohamed, F. A. and Lavernia, E. J. , Particulate Reinforced Metal Matrix Composites—A Review, *Journal of Materials Science* 26(1991), pp. 1137-1156.
2. Gupta, M. , Mohamed, F. A. and Lavernia, E. J. , Heat Transfer Mechanism and Their Effects on Microstructure during Spray Atomization and Co-Deposition of Metal Matrix Composites, *Materials Science and Engineering*, A144(1991), pp. 99-110.
3. Singer, A. R. E, Metal Matrix Composites Made by Spray Forming, *Materials Science and Engineering*, A135(1991), pp. 13-17.
4. Willis, T. C. , Spray Deposition Process for Metal Matrix Composites Manufacture, *Powder Metallurgy*, August 1988, pp. 485-489.
5. Ding, G. L, *SiCp/Al Composites Fabricated by Spray Co-Deposition*, MSc Thesis, pp. 64-86 (in Chinese).

Figure 3 Injection of SiC particulates through a central nozzle inside a liquid metal nozzle

Figure 1 Schematic of spray co-deposition equipment

Figure 2 Tangential injection of SiC particulates

Figure 4 Optical micrograph showing morphology of W60 SiCp/Al composites ($\times 100$)

Figure 5 Optical micrograph showing morphology of W10 SiCp/Al composites ($\times 100$)

Figure 6 Injection of SiC particulates directly from outside

Figure 8 Schematic of the atomized spray field

Figure 9 The radius distribution of particulates' velocity

Figure 10 The radius distribution of particulates' consistency

Figure 7 Optical micrograph showing morphology of W10 SiCp/Al composites ($\times 100$)

Figure 11 Schematic of the forces acting on the SiC particulate